

Multifunctional and flexible phase change composites for dual-mode thermal management of batteries

Lichang Lu

L.lu@lboro.ac.uk

Why managing heat?

- Temperature sensitivity

- Advanced batteries

15-40 °C
Optimal range

Liquid cooling

Aswin et al. Energy Storage. 2020

Air cooling

Aniket. 2021

Miniaturisation

Fast charging

Complex geometries

Xu et al. Nat Comm. 2013

Phase change materials (PCMs)

Heat capacity

Ice: 2.1J/g \longrightarrow Water: 4.2J/g

Fusion latent heat capacity: 334J/g

Culture Insider: How did ancient people escape the summer heat

Lu et al., EcoMat (2025), 7, e70004

- Leakage
- Mechanical rigidity
- Low thermal conduction

What we did?

Phase change composites (PCC)

PCMs: Polyethylene glycol (PEG)

Flexible matrix: Polycaprolactone (PCL)

Nanofillers: Graphene (G) and Carbon nanotubes (C)

PCC x/y -zwt%(G a /C b): x -wt% of matrix, y -wt% of PCMs, z -wt% of nanofillers, $a:b$ -ratio of two fillers

Encapsulation method: Solution casting

- Morphology

Composites properties

- Thermal conductivity

Yang et al., J. Chem. Thermodyn., 2023, 186, 107022.

Leakage proof

Mechanical flexibility

Good thermal conduction

- Mechanical flexibility

- Structural integrity

- Latent heat retention

How do they perform?

- Internal heat

- PCM effectiveness for External abnormal heat thermal management

Cold condition issues
Viscous electrolyte
Reduced kinetics

What sets us apart?

Multifunctionality

Preheating

Early detection

Materials innovation

- Self-regulating heating

- Safety switch & Hazard alert

Lu L. et al. (2025), Adv Sci, e08314

Materials innovation – Hybrid filler system

- Positive temperature coefficient

- Battery performance restoring

Conclusion

Flexible phase change composites

Heating with safety switch

Early detection

Cooling across power outputs

Research interests

Composite materials - Smart and Multifunctional

Manufacturing technique - Ecofriendly and scalable

Acknowledgement

Dr Yi Liu

Dr Ignacio Martin Fabiani

Dr Ashley Fly

Dr Haosong He

Dr Han Zhang

Dr Emiliano Billoti

Prof Ton Peijs

Dr Goran T. Vladislavljević

Nibinar Nizar

Hongxu Guo

Yushen Wang

Guo et al., Adv. Funct. Mater. 35, 2417961 (2025)

Support information

- Testing rig

PCC1500 in liquid state distribution at 50% of SOC, at 3C discharge rate

